

PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATION'S ROLE AND IMPORTANCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL THINKING

Kurbanova Gulnoz Nematovna

DSc of pedagogical sciences, BSMI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7238049>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 03rd October 2022

Accepted: 10th October 2022

Online: 19th October 2022

KEY WORDS

afsona, asotir, xikoyat, doston, soqi, sannovchi, jirov, qalandar, darvesh, san'at, epos, shaman, folklor, dev, pari, ajdar.

ABSTRACT

It is impossible to imagine human development, socialization, formation of an individual as a person, his connection with society without communication. Communication is also a unique need. As the Polish psychologist E. Melibruda [1, p.256] said, interpersonal relationships are as important to us as air. In infancy and adolescence, communication is embodied as an activity that directly affects the leading activity, that is, the formation of new psychological characteristics.

Communication is a multifaceted process of the development of connections between people arising from the needs of joint activities. It is important for everyone to know the rules of communication and develop the skills and abilities to establish it. Each person's own "I" is formed in the process of communication with others, the life paths of a person first develop in the family, kindergarten, school, institute, workplace, among the elderly, that is, in groups and communities. One of our highest spiritual needs is the need for communication.

If our need for communication is not satisfied, our mind will not develop. Therefore, we must always satisfy our communication needs. We get satisfaction from communication with someone, but in some cases we feel unsatisfied.

Communication is the need of people for cooperative activities, and their joint activities related to relationships,

interactions, information and information exchange. When forming personal communication, it is necessary to take into account his age, gender, profession, worldview.

In the current period, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", the national personnel training program, not to be limited to the motivations for choosing a profession, professional training, professional ability and professional skills, but to be professional in the personal activities of future pedagogues. It is emphasized that the formation of culture is an important aspect.

This requires increasing its spiritual content in the entire system of pedagogical dialogue, because pedagogical dialogue is aimed at forming the moral foundations of education.

The complexity of socio-psychological, educational and spiritual tasks places high demands on the teacher's pedagogical

activity. In order for the teacher to achieve high pedagogical and psychological results in his professional activity, it is recommended to use some directions of communication proposed by research scientists based on many years of theoretical and practical experience.

The teacher can create unique features of the upcoming lesson and a pedagogical plan for himself. In it, certain methods of the pedagogical task correspond to each pedagogical task of the lesson, and specific directions of its solution are shown. When planning a lesson, the teacher should not only think about attracting students to the scope of information based on the information about the subject of the lesson, but also find the students who need the teacher's help, to help them. should create conditions, be able to see the conditions that ensure the interest of each student and ensure mutual cooperation.

An important condition for modeling the future communication with students is the mutual emotional unity of the teacher and students, which gives the teacher the opportunity to foresee the following possible atmosphere of the lesson:

- to be able to anticipate various situations that may occur with the student group in the upcoming lesson;
- organization of various levels of democratic and free interaction with students, setting prospects for its development;
- to create students' interest in learning and creative mood in the lesson[2].

It is very important to model future communication with teachers in the course of the lesson, because this process comprehensively determines the didactic principles of the lesson, directs the teacher to creative activity, in which there is an

opportunity to improve various models of communication in relation to the perfect forms of interaction with students. will be

Communication modeling can be done quickly right before a new lesson, and sometimes it takes on a permanent character. It creates an opportunity for the teacher to foresee his pedagogical attitude and emotional behavior and feelings in the course of the lesson. The conditions and system of future communication will be determined, and a pre-planned communication model will be implemented.

In the first moments of the pedagogical dialogue, the teacher should clarify the possibilities of using the selected educational methods, feel the general mood of the students, their creativity and diligence.

Pedagogical communication is a unique example of teacher's creativity in terms of its structure. Pedagogical scientists describe many descriptions of the teacher's communication with students in their scientific works, but communication is first of all a personal psychological feature of the teacher.

Scientists only give direction to the teacher for communication. In particular, the Russian pedagogue V.A. According to Kan-Kalik, the structure of the teacher's pedagogical communication is carried out in the following directions [3]:

1. Prognostic stage (modeling) - modeling of future communication by the teacher with the group team.
2. Pedagogical communication - achieving the organization of direct communication with the student during the initial mutual acquaintance process.
3. Pedagogical process - teacher's actions, pedagogical skills should be aimed directly at communication management.

4. Analysis of the results - analysis of the communication carried out, objective evaluation of achievements and shortcomings, modeling for future activities.

Based on the above mentioned points of view of the scientist, these directions of communication can be described as follows. At the modeling stage, the audience should respond to all standards, study the psychological characteristics of each student, anticipate and eliminate the dynamics of difficulties that may be encountered in the educational process, build communication on the basis of mutual cooperation, i.e. it is necessary to ensure that the communication is appropriate not only to the personality of the teacher, but also to the personality of the student.

At the stage of pedagogical communication, it is necessary to master the interview technique that quickly engages the group in mutual communication, to be able to respond to all their interests, to create an opportunity for them to freely express their opinions, and to master the methods of applying various methods of positively influencing the minds of students.

At the stage of the pedagogical process, the teacher's activity is to direct educational work in a certain direction, to support the initiative of students, to organize a fair dialogue with the official and unofficial leaders of the group, to share their opinions with the opinions of the team. activities such as creating skills to adapt to real conditions are carried out.

According to the analysis of the obtained results, the teacher should objectively evaluate his activity, take into account the achievements and shortcomings, know how to critically apply

it in the future educational activities, ensure the unity of goals, plans and results in this direction, he should know how to lead and take initiative in organizing and managing communication with students in the educational process.

Modern socio-psychological studies show that a person can be the initiator of communication, and sometimes, depending on the situation, participate as an active or passive subject of interaction [4].

Pedagogically correct organization of communication in the professional activity of a teacher places serious demands on his pedagogical culture. Lessons and educational events are a process that forms the system of mutual relations between the teacher and the student, and it is in this activity that the teacher forms his personal pedagogical activity.

From mutual conversations with experienced teachers, it is known that in order to choose the form of communication with the student group in the lesson, the teacher is required to choose pedagogical methods for the new material being studied. Therefore, when preparing to learn a new topic in the lesson and creating a plan of educational influence, it is necessary to model the rich aspects of the communication system [5].

A young teacher, who is just beginning his pedagogical career, may face specific psychological obstacles in the process of interaction with students, especially in his professional pedagogical behavior, he knows that conflicts may arise in communication with students, and every should be trained, have deep pedagogical and psychological knowledge.

A young teacher may not have communication skills, which causes negative situations such as being confused

and unable to move freely. Young teachers lack advanced expressive means of communication, do not know how to use speech techniques, inaccuracy in mime and pantomimic actions. Sometimes, as a result of the teacher's use of the "authoritarian style" of communication in the educational process, the relationship has negative consequences.

Due to the deep knowledge and skills of a young teacher, educational tasks, various tasks and educational activities, conducted pedagogical activities may not be interesting for students or they may be completely indifferent. Taking advantage of unexpected and unprepared pedagogical problems is a huge test in the teacher's professional activity and is of fundamental importance, because in such situations it is impossible to roughly plan all options of communication. In this case, the teacher must also have the ability to develop skills in situations of pedagogical improvisation (without preparation) in communication - quickly and truthfully assess the situation and students' behavior with deep understanding, without any logical reasoning, his knowledge and skills, Based on his experiences, pedagogical skills and intelligence, he should make a quick and clear decision, adjust his attitude and personal pedagogical activity depending on the change of the situation, and organically apply this decision in the process of communication with students.

At this point, it is important to note that the teacher should take into account the following situations:

- teachers should follow the culture of communication from the very beginning of their educational activities, in this process they should plan their daily interactions with the teacher and the student team

depending on the situation, pay attention to every action, the tone of words, and learn the best features of traditional communication. mastery;

- recording various situations in the group based on dialogue, comparing the previous state of the students' behavior with the state after the educational activity and evaluating it;

- analyzing the results of one's own communication style from a critical point of view, continuously eliminating shortcomings. Creating the necessary words, pleasant tone of voice, behavior;

- it is not enough to know its conditions for the effective development of the culture of pedagogical communication, it is necessary to start interaction with students in the tradition of "teacher-student" and solve important tasks based on mutual exchange of ideas. attract the attention of the ect;

- what should be understood by the object of communication, i.e. attracting the student's attention? The meaning of this is that the teacher demonstrates his skills with his politeness, culture, good manners, and the ability to find a way to the hearts of students in communication, and takes the socio-psychological basis for the organizational forms of communication culture.

In order to have a pedagogical effect based on the indicated situations, special requirements are placed on the teacher's culture of pedagogical communication, ethics and manners, and cordiality. These qualities are a guarantee of success in the teacher's ability to communicate with the group, parents, organize and manage educational activities with students with a specific goal in mind.

A young teacher working in medical educational institutions that adheres to the

culture of pedagogical communication, which is a unique quality of professional activity, should embody the following characteristics:

- a socially-politically active person with high spiritual level views, strong and stable faith, loyalty to the ideals of our state, national idea and ideology of independence, patriotism, self-sacrifice formed in accordance with the socio-political demands and needs of our country to be;
- the formation of sincere love for students, the ability to understand all their needs, interests, motivations and behavior;
- Pedagogical observation of events in society, events in the world, nature, existence, interpersonal, inter-group, inter-ethnic relations, the ability to aspire to innovation, creative research;
- to be able to react rationally and intelligently to any emergency situations, news happening in society and socio-economic changes, to be able to set the right goals, make a plan, direct control to be able to do, manage and demonstrate their capabilities;
- demonstrate the ability to organize and manage pedagogical activities, public system, temporary group relations, mass movements; the breadth of the worldview and the scope of thinking, the wide interest in learning worldly knowledge, the tendency to scientific research, the level of certain scientific potential and pedagogical skills are regularly increased;
- ability to communicate with students, logically concise, meaningful, effective speech culture, equipped with psychological influence, etc [6].

In the content of such orientation, the content and essence of the reforms carried out by the society in the field of education are expressed. Therefore, in the essence of

the teacher's work, there should be criteria such as intellectual consciousness, high spirituality, national worldview and faith based on age-old traditions and universal values, nourished by the advanced achievements of the time, which show his spiritual level. need

The problem of forming the personality of a future teacher is solved based on the needs and requirements of any individual society. Therefore, in the new Law "On Education" to be adopted at the present time and the normative documents adopted on the basis of this law, it is necessary not to be limited to the motives of choosing a profession, professional training, professional ability and professional skills, but also It is emphasized that the formation of professional thinking in the future pedagogical personnel is an absolutely necessary condition.

In our republic, a number of scientific researches have been carried out in various periods regarding the specific ethnopsychological qualities, characteristics, abilities, working methods, ways to achieve mastery, and interpersonal communication norms of the teaching profession.

Communication is a process of interaction between communication subjects, during this interaction information is exchanged, relations are established and developed. Collaborative activities are organized and implemented through communication. At the same time, during the activity, new relations and connections are formed between people. So, communication and activity are closely related.

It should be mentioned that the realization of the educational potential of communication is largely determined by the

personal qualities of the teacher. A properly chosen method of pedagogical communication, consistent with the unique individuality of the pedagogue, helps to solve the following set of tasks:

1. pedagogical influence becomes the same thing as the personality of the pedagogue, the process of communicating with the audience becomes simpler, it becomes pleasant and organic for the pedagogue;
2. the process of establishing mutual relations with students becomes much easier;

thirdly, the effectiveness of all the most important tasks of pedagogical communication increases, at the same time, all this happens on the positive basis of emotional calmness of the pedagogue at all stages of communication.

The methodology of forming an individual style of communication in students includes the following stages:

1. To study the real personal characteristics of the individual style of communication of students and their understanding by students. It is carried out on the basis of independent analysis of students, comprehensive descriptions of each other, observations of teachers. For this purpose, students asked "How am I in communication with other people?" they write essays on the topic, prepare descriptions for each other with a similar content, etc.
2. Identifying and eliminating shortcomings in personal communication: overcoming shyness, shyness, negative situations in the communication style.
3. Tasks on developing an emotionally comfortable style of communication for a

teacher and their comparison with self-observation data.

4. Work in the field of mastering the components of pedagogical communication based on one's own individual style of communication (in special training).
5. In accordance with one's own style of communication, work on learning the whole phenomenon of pedagogical communication and clarifying the style of communication (in special trainings).
6. Communicating with students based on an individual style of real pedagogical activity, strengthening this style (during pedagogical practice and internship).

It is necessary for teachers who are just starting to work in medical colleges to regularly work on the formation of individual communication style.

Aspects of pedagogical communication play an important role in the organization of the educational process, they are related to the direct interaction of the pedagogue and students. Here are some steps.

The first stage is the educator's awareness of the situation of the educational process, this process requires the pedagogue to restore the previous features of communication with the group in his memory, to record the situation of communication, to quickly compare it with the previous situation of the interaction, with the previously planned example of this action, z involves clarifying the communication style. It should be noted that this stage passes very quickly, and at the same stage, the necessary words, tone, behavior should appear.

Second stage - for the effective process of pedagogical communication, it is not enough to know its conditions. The beginning of interaction with students is related to solving another important task of

exchange of ideas and attracting the attention of the object of communication. What should be understood by attracting the attention of the object of communication, that is, the student? The meaning of this is to draw the attention of students, which is necessary for conducting the lesson, to take the social-psychological basis for the future interaction, the planned methods of education, organizational forms. Often, young pedagogues think that

students should always pay attention to the teacher and do not solve these important tasks of mutual exchange of ideas with a steady step.

The indicated stages of direct communication are relatively independent of pedagogical influence, they are repeated from time to time in each form, they should be taken into account when organizing the educational process.

Figure 2.1.1. The purpose of pedagogical communication.

In connection with the importance of communication in the organization of educational influence, special demands are placed on the culture of pedagogical communication, the educator's cordiality, cordiality is manifested in it as professional thinking. An educator should be able to communicate with people in the process of team, group and individual work, organize it with students with a specific goal in mind, and manage them. The following criteria of professional pedagogic harmony, which a young teacher follows, can be singled out: the presence of a stable need for regular communication with students in various

fields, the manifestation of emotional calmness at all stages of communication, qualities related to mutual exchange of ideas, availability of skills and qualifications.

Teachers of future medical institutions should be sharply distinguished by the following characteristics, and these characteristics determine the main criteria of their professional thinking:

- views of a high spiritual level that correspond to the requirements and needs of our independent republic, strong and stable faith, loyalty to the ideals of our great country, the national idea and ideology of

independence, the formation of feelings of patriotism, self-sacrifice, perfectly reflecting the sense of community, social - being a politically active person;

- warm and sincere love for children, students, and even all members of our society, the ability to understand their needs, interests, motivations, and behavior;

- pedagogical observation, i.e., perceptive (sensitivity to perception) ability in relation to social events, situations, nature and realities, existence, interpersonal, inter-group, inter-national relations;

- the ability to rationally understand the characteristics of people's actions and relationships in one or another aspect of life and activity, to direct them to identification and reflection;

- the ability to effectively aim, set goals, plan, direct control, manage and express oneself in emergency situations, changing conditions;

- mastery of organization and management skills in pedagogical activities, temporary group relations in the public system, public actions;

- the breadth of the scope of general interest, the variety of interests related to knowledge, the ability to conduct scientific research, the achievement of certain potential, skill levels;

- being equipped with communication etiquette, speech culture, logically concise, strong meaning, effective transfer of ideas, ability to influence;

In our opinion, it is a professional necessity for a modern teacher to be able to convey correct, effective information during communication and to be able to convince the interlocutor.

I can recommend the following program for mutual exchange of ideas in the

process of formation of professional thinking:

1. Self-awareness from a professional point of view (identification of one's own qualities, positive and weak points for mutual exchange of ideas in communication) and the program of self-education through mutual exchange of ideas on this basis development. In this place, it is appropriate to evaluate one's personality in the following directions, to analyze the experience, it is appropriate with students, to analyze the experience of sensations obtained in communication with people, to analyze the current level of previous communication in communication with people, communication to analyze one's own ideal perceptions about, to analyze perceptions of how others (students, teachers) evaluate your communication capabilities.

2. Working on the basis of specialized exercises to develop the main features of self-confidence.

3. Carrying out various public works with students and people, in which the experience of exchange of ideas (lectures, conversations) is formed.

4. To create a system of situations that form the experience of overcoming negative moods in communication and develop cordiality.

Based on the fundamental changes in the field of education and training of Uzbekistan, the realization of the goal and the achievement of a guaranteed result in education at the present time, the cooperative activity of both the teacher and the student and the goal set by them, remains dependent on the chosen content, method, form, tool. But there is the most important tool for the realization of these goals, which ensures the quality and

efficiency of the educational process. This is the ethics of communication [7, p. 59-62].

Forming the ethics of communication among today's youth, taking into account their age characteristics, is important for their development as mature professionals in the future. President Sh.M. Mirziyoev in his speeches and lectures emphasizes that this is an important condition for renewing the pedagogue's pedagogical communication, that is, today's intense life requires people who can easily communicate with people, who can distinguish good from bad, We demand to educate and raise a perfect generation who is able to find the right path with intelligence and intelligence.

Communication is a multifaceted process of the development of bonds between people arising from the needs of joint activity. Communication (relationship) involves the exchange of information between those who work together. This takes into account the communicative aspect of the relationship. People turn to language first when entering into a relationship.

Another aspect of communication is the mutual action of the participants in the relationship - in the process of speech, they exchange not only words, but also actions. For example, when we enter into a relationship, we communicate with gestures if he is satisfied with us. The next aspect of the relationship is the ability of the participants to perceive each other. For example, we treat a person with respect or contempt before starting a conversation.

So, in the process of communication, communicative (information transfer), interactive (mutual action) and perceptive (mutual) perception is carried out.

There are 5 stages of professional-pedagogical communication. These are:

1. Orientation (getting a goal) during the communication process. At this stage, the awareness of the pedagogue's communication emerges. Also, the determination of the communication style in the new communicative activity conditions is revealed.

2. An important aspect of pedagogical activity is attracting attention, and in order to effectively communicate with the student, the student's attention must be stable during the lesson.

3. The stage of conquering the heart of the object (person) is of great importance in the organization of pedagogical communication. In essence, this stage is a stage of a unique search for communication. For example, when explaining new material, the pedagogue prepares students for communication. The teacher's understanding of the student is the key to professional-pedagogical communication.

4. Another stage of pedagogical communication is verbal communication, that is, the pedagogue presents the new material orally to the students. Speech communication is very important for a teacher. In the pedagogical communication system, the words of the pedagogue are considered to be the trigger of images.

5. Communicative means of observing excitement play an important role in the interaction between the teacher and the listener. In particular, the speech of the pedagogue should be lively, rich in tones, understandable, clear, simple language. Then the audience's perception will be complete and vivid [8, p.170].

The teacher should allow the student to concentrate. In order to understand each other, it is worth mentioning the following 5 conditions:

- having a common professional language;

- taking into account the level of intelligence;
- completeness of information;
- logical explanation;
- ability to concentrate.

It is important to know the social and psychological conditions of working with the audience, the methods of active teaching and the methods of their organization for the effectiveness of educational activities, and they should be focused on forming a culture of behavior in students. There are types of debates that can be used to solve any problem, and mainly the rules of conducting an oral debate, which directly help in the formation of communication ethics in students.

The main tasks of communication ethics are expressed in the following:

- 1) studying the laws of interpersonal interaction and communication in the process of joint activity;
- 2) to analyze the views of Eastern scholars about communication;
- 3) emphasizing the availability of communication opportunities encouraging the student to be active;
- 4) formation of communication aimed at activating the professional ability of students;
- 5) acquiring the role of communication in coordinating interpersonal relations;
- 6) consideration of some consequences of interaction. We need to develop the following communication skills in future professionals:
 - theoretical foundations of communication culture;
 - rules of interpersonal relations;
 - the rules of pedagogical communication;
 - should have an idea about the main requirements for communication in the family, groups and communities;

- studying the formation of communication in a person;
- formation of communication culture in all groups and communities;
- observing the importance of communication in interpersonal relations;
- to know and use the secrets of communication;
- carrying out methods of communication formation in groups;
- to learn about the culture of communication in the family, the secrets of communication;
- formation of skills in the organization of psychological consultations in order to form a culture of communication [9, p. 142].

Communication, on the basis of external influences and examples, prepares a thorough ground for self-correction, re-education, realization of personal potential, leads to perfection. The main reason for the inability to communicate is the wrong attitude towards oneself and the people around one due to overestimation or underestimation of one's self. There are ways to prevent this, and focusing mainly on the following will lead to positive outcomes:

- 1) organization of humane relations between all members of the communication process through the communication system in partnership activities, creating the possibility of comparison of emotional environment.
- 2) implementation of measures aimed at ensuring a favorable position of each member in the system of internal relations in communication.
- 3) organizing special trainings on acquiring information about the features, manners, methods, and forms of human communication.
- 4) creation of business games, psychodrama, training system designed for

interpersonal relations and communication methods.

It is important to include game and non-game forms in teaching communication:

1. Introducing elements of informal communication into the lesson. At the same time, the use of didactic games, in which the role of the dialogue organizer is performed by one of the students, not the teacher.
2. Focus on the positive aspects of the answer. Students are specially trained to objectively evaluate the answers of their peers, while paying attention to the smallest details and learning to single out the most successful aspects of their peers' answers. Arguing about how to overcome the shortcomings, i.e., influencing one student by telling them about it.

3. Social relations between people have their own characteristics in the East. This study guide will help to understand the psychological nature of the changes taking place in the human spirituality and psyche during the period of the renewal of the society.

Working on the basis of this proposed system accelerates the formation of empathy, which is a personal quality of a pedagogue.

Shortly speaking, professional thinking, based on the culture of communication, expresses the future teacher's worldview, his desire for maturity through his love for his profession, his sense of existence, his sense of necessity for the interests and development of the Motherland, society.

References:

1. Melibruda, E. Ya – Ty – My: Psikhologicheskie vozmozhnosti uluchsheniya obshcheniya : per. s polsk. / E. in Melibru. - M.: Progress, 1986. - 256 p.
2. Grekhnev V.S. Kultura pedagogicheskogo obshcheniya: Kniga dlya uchitelya. - M.: "Prosveshchenie", 1990
3. Azizkhojaeva N.N. Pedagogical technology and pedagogical skill - T.: TDPU, 2003.
4. Bykov A.K. Teoriya i praktika razvitiya pedagogicheskogo masterstva prepodavateley vyshey voennoy shkoly. // Diss. dr. ped. science - M., 2000.
5. Begimkulov U.Sh. Theory and practice of organization and management of informatization of pedagogical educational processes. // Ped. doctor of science scientific school. diss for - T., 2007.
6. Sultonova G.A. Pedagogical skills. - T.: TDPU named after Nizami, 2005
7. Ishmuhamedov R., Yuldashev M. Innovative pedagogical technologies in education and training. - Tashkent, Sparks of Literature, 2017. - P.59-62.
8. Ismailova Z.K. Methodology of educational work. - Tashkent, Istiklal, 2003. - 170 p.
9. Ochilova G. Basics of pedagogical skills. Text of lectures. - Tashkent, TDIU, 2012. - 142 p.
10. Khoshimova M.K. Pedagogical technologies and pedagogical skills. - Tashkent, TDIU, 2011.- 160 p.
11. G.N. Development of professional thinking of students through pedagogical communication Monograph "Durdona", Bukhara-2021.
12. Kurbanova G.N. Pedagogical and psychological bases on developing students' professional thinking in medical pedagogical education. International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation, Vol. 24, Issue 06, 2020. 3059-3067

13. Kurbanova G.N. The role of ancestral heritage in the development of professional thinking of future professionals International Scientific Journal Theoretical & Applied Science p-ISSN: 2308-4944 (print) e-ISSN: 2409-0085 (online) Year: 2020 Issue: 01 Volume: 81 Published: 30.01.2020 <http://T-Science.org>. SOI: 1.1/TAS DOI: 10.15863

14. Курбанова Г.Н. Развитие профессионального и оперативного мышления будущих специалистов в образовательном процессе. Neurodynamics журнал клинической психологии и психиатрии// Т.2 №1.2020, 50-56.ISSN 2658-7955 Адрес: <https://smu.psychiatr.ru/neurodynamics>